

Peer Life Coaching, Personal, and Reciprocal Relationship Among Junior High School Students of Looc Integrated School

Cherry DP. Del Campo

HR Manager/ College Instructor, St. Vincent College of Cabuyao, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The study assessed peer life coaching and the personal and reciprocal relationship among high school students. Primary data were utilized in the study by obtaining information of the level of awareness while personal and reciprocal relationship of students were obtained through the use of a validated survey questionnaire. The data were tallied and statistically analyzed using frequency, weighted mean, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The findings of the study revealed that the student-respondents were aware of peer life coaching in terms of individual relationships, group leadership, leadership discussion, advisory, tutorial, and human interpersonal relationships. Good personal and reciprocal relationships were noted among the students. Further, peer life coaching was found to be positively correlated with the personal and reciprocal relationships of the students. A guidance program was developed which aimed to improve the level of awareness of peer life coaching and the students' personal and reciprocal relationships.

Keywords: *Peer life coaching, personal relationship, reciprocal relationship.*

Citation: Cherry DP. Del Campo (2021). Peer Life Coaching, Personal, and Reciprocal Relationship Among Junior High School Students of Looc Integrated School. *International Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Studies*, 3(4), 80-106.

INTRODUCTION

Guidance and counseling are part of the services provided by the school, as mandated by the law. It involves using an integrated approach towards developing a well-functioning individual primarily by helping students develop their potentials to the fullest, plan their prospects to the fullest, and plan their future by their abilities, interests, and needs (RA 9258 Sec.3). The state's vital role is recognized by the state (RA Sec. 2) as it promotes an essential role in shaping young Filipinos that help in nation-building.

The school's role in promoting social development, emotional balance, and psychological resilience in children at risk of socio-emotional difficulties is rising worldwide [1]. Thus, under DepEd's staffing standard, public and private elementary and high schools must hire one guidance counselor for every 500 students. In the school setting, the most commonly used form of counseling is individual and group counseling. In the conduct of group counseling sessions in schools, many issues can be discussed. As such, group counseling is a time-efficient exercise. Multiple students of similar ages who are dealing with similar problems are grouped to accomplish similar goals. In the Philippine school set up expressly in public schools where a high enrolment rate is observed, the counselor cannot address all the arising problems regarding students' personalities.

The Department of Education is committed to protecting and promoting Filipino learners' rights to complete quality and equitable education. Further, the department aims to pursue this without jeopardizing the learners' health [2]. Health concerns among students include their emotional and psychological development, which are integral parts of their well-being. Although the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004, also known as RA 9258, was crafted and designed to professionalize the practice of guidance and counseling in the Philippines, public and private schools find it hard to comply with DepEd's standards. As a result, schools must look for various ways and means to ensure that guidance and counseling will still be effective despite the limitation of available licensed guidance counselors to accommodate all the students in the school.

One program that promotes guidance and counseling that schools can implement is peer life coaching. Peer life coaching encompasses helping relationships individually (one-to-one helping relationship), group leadership, leadership discussions, advisory, tutorial, and human interpersonal activities. All the activities under peer life coaching aim to assist learners in addressing their various concerns. Peer life coaching is essentially about problem-solving skills and active

listening in providing support to one's peers. Peer life coaching is a way for teens to learn how to pay attention and help other children, especially in applying the strategies in their everyday lives.

Peer support begins with the natural willingness of most young people to act in a cooperative and friendly way towards one another. Peer counseling and support systems build on this intrinsic quality and create structures that facilitate the young person's potential for responsible, sensitive, and empathic caring. Based on the premise that classmates and friends are the ones students often confide in and rely upon. Further, their peers are more visible and available, especially during moments when difficulty arises. At that point, instead of passively standing by and watching or actively colluding with those who contribute to the problem, they can reach out to offer understanding, friendship, and a listening heart.

Since peers are often considered the most powerful influence, especially among junior high school students, this study aimed to assess the students' level of awareness on peer life coaching in terms of individual relationships, group leadership, leadership discussion, advisory, tutorial, and human interpersonal activity. The study extends to assess how these peer life coaching activities are related to the personal and reciprocal relationship among junior high school students of Loooc Integrated School.

Theoretical Framework

According to Bandura [3], the Social Learning Theory posits that people learn from one another via observation, imitation, and modeling. The theory has often been called a bridge between behaviorist and cognitive learning theories because it encompasses attention, memory, and motivation. People learn through observing others' behavior, attitudes, and outcomes of those behaviors [3]. Bandura highlighted that most human behavior is learned observationally through modeling: from observing others, one forms an idea of how new behaviors are performed, and on later occasions, this coded information serves as a guide for action. Social learning theory explains human behavior in terms of continuous reciprocal interaction between cognitive, behavioral, and environmental influences.

Reciprocal determinism believed that one's world influences a person's behavior and vice versa. Personality is the result of interaction between the environment, behavior, and psychological processes or one's ability to entertain images in minds and language [3].

Social interaction and collaboration are essential components of situated learning [4]. Learners become involved in a community of practice that incorporates certain beliefs and behaviors to be acquired. As the beginner or novice moves from the periphery of a community to its center, he or she becomes more active and engaged within the culture and eventually assumes the role of an expert.

Social interaction and collaboration are essential components of situated learning [4]. Learners become involved in a community of practice that incorporates certain beliefs and behaviors to be acquired. As the beginner or novice moves from the periphery of a community to its center, he or she becomes more active and engaged within the culture and eventually assumes the role of an expert.

For peer counseling and mentoring, the peers must develop respect and proper human interaction. It allows students to acknowledge similarities and differences in the developmental issues that everyone deals with. The development of camaraderie and acceptance often helps struggling students gain confidence in themselves and perform better in school. The feeling of having friends in a setting is a critical component of self-esteem, which in turn is a necessary condition for comfort and success. Thus, peer counseling and mentoring create a personal and reciprocal relationship evident in the given theories.

On the other hand, reciprocity is a social norm of responding to a positive action with another positive action, which in essence is rewarding kind actions. As a social construct, reciprocity means that people are frequently more excellent and cooperative in response to social actions than predicted by the self-interest model. Conversely, in response to hostile actions, they are frequently more nasty and even brutal. Reciprocity makes it possible to build continuing relationships and exchanges.

Bandura [3] believes in "reciprocal determinism," which is essentially about a person's world that causes one's behavior. Behaviorism, on the other hand, essentially states that one's environment causes one's behavior. In his study about adolescent aggression, Bandura [3] emphasized that behavior causes the environment. In his further analysis of one's behavior and environment, Bandura [3] identified personality as an interaction between three components: the environment, behavior, and psychological processes (one's ability to entertain images in minds and language).

Figure 1 presents the research paradigm. As presented in the figure, the independent variable of the study contains peer life coaching. This is comprised of (1) individual relationships, (2) group leadership, (3) leadership discussion, (4) advisory, (5) tutorial, and (6) human interpersonal activity. The dependent variables are personal relationship (positive attitude, diversity, building relationship) and reciprocal relationship (emotional intelligence, teamwork, empathy, integrity, social boldness).

Figure1. Research Paradigm

Statement of the Problem

This study focused on peer life coaching and mentoring toward the development of personal and reciprocal relationships among junior high school students of Looc Integrated School.

Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of manifestation of Peer Life Coaching strategies among junior high school students of Looc Integrated School in terms of:
 - 1.1 Individual Relationship,
 - 1.2 Group Leadership,
 - 1.3 Leadership Discussion,
 - 1.4 Advisory,
 - 1.5 Tutorial, and
 - 1.6 Human Interpersonal Activity?

2. How do student respondents describe their personal relationship as to:
 - 2.1 Positive Attitude,
 - 2.2 Diversity, and
 - 2.3 Building Relationship?

3. What is the level of the reciprocal relationship of the student respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1 Emotional Intelligence,
 - 3.2 Team Work,
 - 3.3 Empathy,
 - 3.4 Integrity, and
 - 3.5 Social Boldness?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of peer life coaching and personal relationship?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of peer life coaching and reciprocal relationship?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what guidance program can be proposed towards the improvement of peer life coaching among junior high school students of Looc Integrated School?

Hypotheses

The researcher posited the following hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between the level of manifestation on peer life coaching and the personal relationship among junior high school students of Looc Integrated School.
2. There is no significant relationship between the level of manifestation on peer life coaching and the reciprocal relationship among junior high school students of Looc Integrated School.

Scope and Delimitations

For the clarity of focus, this research was guided by the following scope and limitations: (1) the research revolved to selected junior high school students of Looc Integrated School, and (2) the focus of the study was on investigating the level of awareness on peer life coaching and the level of manifestation of personal and reciprocal relationships among junior high school students of Looc Integrated School.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

The researcher described the facets of the main problem, its current situation, and its variables through related literature and studies sourced mainly in books, journals, the internet, and other studies. The review is divided into three sections: (1) Background of Peer Life Coaching, (2) Personal Relationship, and (3) Reciprocal Relationship.

Peer Life Coaching

Peer coaching has been described as a relationship between teachers based on sharing experiences, practices, and planning, with learning taking place through observation and skills transfer. This technique has been used to facilitate the implementation of new practices and approaches within teaching. The UK Department of Education strongly endorses peer coaching to enhance the professional development of teachers. In the US, large corporations such as Microsoft sponsor programs to promote the positive benefits of peer-coaching interaction between teachers [5].

Our study adds to the existing literature by documenting an improvement in students' coaching effectiveness over the semester and identifying the most critical factors contributing to this improvement. We identify the rationale for the development of the peer coaching process and its learning objectives and describe the employment of the peer coaching process. We found that training, structured peer feedback, supporting handouts, and consistent peer coaching practice were the most critical factors to becoming an effective peer coach. The most challenging factors to students in becoming an effective peer coaches were developing their ability to effectively listen to their peers and the fear of asking their partner challenging or probing questions. Rather than listening, students found themselves interjecting their opinions, offering advice, talking about themselves, or relating what their partners were saying to their own lives, if only in their minds. We found the most compelling aspects of students' peer coaching in supporting peers' leadership development: being nonjudgmental, listening, accountable, and asking questions. We present suggestions to prepare instructors and students to employ a peer coaching process and possible adaptations [6].

The peer coaching model (See Figure 1) evolved from peer education research that has been empirically supported to improve academic performance amongst the general student body. However, it should be noted that distinctions exist between the proposed model and previous peer education models. The first distinction is that peer education focuses on academic tasks while peer coaching focuses on athletic tasks. The distinction is evident when reviewing academic sports journals where coaches are always referred to as "the coach" and never teacher or educator. Peer education allows individuals to support the growth of those who are less skilled by educating those individuals regarding ways to master academic content (i.e., human anatomy, math, etc.). Peer coaching, on the contrary, can be understood as a developmental exercise in which individual student-athletes work to "coach" their teammates regarding ways to improve their athletic performance. The coach, in essence, designs the exercises for the athletes but does not necessarily teach the exercises (i.e., require endurance activities, conduct throwing drills, Etc.). The coach is also not superior at the exercise, which is often the case when referring to someone as an educator [7].

Individual Relationship. The main objective of higher education institutions is to educate students to high standards to perform their role in society proficiently. Elsewhere we presented empirical evidence illustrating that using a blended learning approach to the learning process that applies a moderate constructivist e-learning instructional model improves students' academic outcomes. In this article, we use social network analysis techniques to analyze how social relationships improve student knowledge building with the deployment of this teaching/learning model. This study suggests that the teaching/ learning model used promotes the social relationship of discussion and the generation of new

ideas, and this relationship has an impact on improving students' academic outcomes. We also illustrate that advice-seeking and trust among students are the relationships that most influence the discussion and generation of new ideas. We conclude by proposing learning strategies designed to improve these social relationships [8].

Group Leadership. The effort to build leadership character that has been explained can be filled in guidance and counseling service. One way of the service that can be given to college students to develop their leadership character is to improve their mental health. The reason is that a college student is included in the future development of early adulthood with the duty of development is “to develop the interpersonal communication proficiency and to learn to associate with colleagues individually and in the group”. It is possible to be given to college students because it suits the development characteristic guidance and counseling methods to make the college students develop their cooperation, communication, and reception proficiency. It is contentedly without feeling bored performing activities involving themselves and their colleagues in college or organization contexts [9].

Leadership Discussion. The leaders feel that it is positive learning support for the students. They perceive the guidance they provide as contributing to student understanding and a sense of academic confidence. As such, they feel that the students gradually contribute more to the discussions. They do not always perceive the students as feeling confident initially, but they grow from their participation in any case. “You see that they are proud, in a way. They become a bit more enthusiastic about taking part in the teaching and talk and say what they think”. The leaders believe that it gives the students self-confidence, both academically and personally. The students also develop independence. In this way, the guidance contributes to a self-development process. Contributing to student development is the leaders’ primary motivation. They also see that this is a two-way job and contribution. “When you see that it works, that is a bonus in itself. That’s what is fun. When I can help them to understand it and that we both make it work from our different positions” [10].

Advisory. A second draw of the peer advising program was the opportunity to Meet with a peer whom they felt could relate to and help process and navigate issues they were experiencing as a new college student. One student felt pressure to compete for internships and career-related opportunities. Another felt out of place because he perceived himself to be of a different socioeconomic background from his peers. Another student struggled socially and noted being frustrated because the student thought “college would automatically be great because it is college.” The invitation to meet with a peer advisor came as a timely and useful offer of support in a time of need for these students. Overall, the interview transcripts demonstrate that respondents perceived peer advising to be effective, timely, and delivered by a member of the campus community equipped to relate to the experiences of new college students [11].

Tutorial. Peer tutoring can be applied among students of the same age group or students from different age groups. The students learn from each other in an organized way through the process. It is a well-organized and beneficial learning experience in which one student acts as the tutor or teacher, and the other serves as the tutee or learner. Peer tutoring creates an opportunity for the students to utilize their knowledge and experience in a meaningful way. In this process, the tutors reinforce their learning through reviewing and reformulating their knowledge.

Human Interpersonal Activity. The ability to communicate is an essential ability that a human must-have. Interpersonal communication will contribute to initiating and maintaining social relationships with other people. Interpersonal communication is also beneficial for organizations in achieving their goals. Interpersonal communication is also one of the determinants of the recruiter in choosing prospective workers because someone who has good communication skills will determine the productivity level of that person in an institution or organization. Unfortunately, the urgency of the importance of interpersonal communication skills is not accompanied by facts about existing interpersonal communication skills, and the fact is that students' interpersonal communication skills in Indonesia are low [12].

Personal Relationship

Client and coach can explore the interaction between their own two strength-type combinations to enhance the coaching relationship by promoting better rapport and communication. Similarly, the client’s ability to interact with others may be boosted by awareness of strength-type combinations. Various niche applications have developed within the life coaching industry, such as retirement coaching, relationship coaching, and financial coaching. One emerging specialized area lies within the educational setting. Life coaching within educational settings is distinct from educational coaching (or tutoring), specifically aimed at improving academic performance [13].

Autonomy involves considering the student's perspectives, providing relevant information and opportunities for student choice, and initiating and regulating their behaviors. Establishing a personal connection and addressing our students' basic psychological needs will improve our teaching, inspire and engage our students and promote positive attitudes towards teaching and learning while reducing competition and increasing compassion. These are important

goals because unless students are inspired and motivated and have positive attitudes towards teaching and learning, our efforts will fail to meet their full potential [14].

Positive Attitude. Learner diversity is an issue worth addressing in education practices across countries if inclusive societies are developed, promoted, and sustained. Towards realizing inclusive societies, employing inclusive best practices in education systems would be an essential foremost step. Inclusive education is a process that involves the transformation of schools and other centers of learning to cater to all children: boys and girls, students from various ethnic groups and linguistic minorities, rural populations, and those who have exceptional learning needs. In the context of Tanzania, inclusive education is viewed as a system of education in which all children, youths, and adults are enrolled, actively participate and achieve in regular schools and other educational programs regardless of their diverse backgrounds and abilities. Without discrimination, through minimization of barriers and maximization of resources. Inclusive education facilitates learning opportunities for all youths and adults as well. It aims to eliminate exclusion resulting from negative attitudes and lack of response to diversity in race, economic status, social class, ethnicity, language, religion, gender, sexual orientation, and ability [15].

Building Relationship. Further, using a range of crucial coaching communication skills such as listening, questioning, giving feedback, and analytical skills were deemed fundamental to relationship success. Basic communication skills, including probing, summarizing, paraphrasing, and providing client affirmation, were emphasized as essential to building the relationship. The ability to embed different tools and techniques into the coaching sessions was also considered necessary for the students concerning opening up the reflective dialogue. The different tools allowed for variety and the engagement of different learning preferences with techniques involved in writing activities, coaching apps, or using holistic approaches that engaged the mind and the body (e.g., two chair work). Evidence of this is noted here [16].

Reciprocal Relationship

Reciprocal peer coaching (RPC) is another term often used in the literature, and it can be regarded as a form of peer-assisted learning that can encourage individual students to coach each other in turn so that the outcome of the process is a more rounded understanding and skillful execution of the task. Novices are encouraged to work with each other in conjunction with the support and guidance of a tutor. Each student has a vested interest in their learning and the learning of other group members. To meet individual goals, they are all working with each other collaboratively and cooperatively. Similarly, in 2006, RPC was found to enhance the depth of learning in executive education. It was reported increases in motivational learning and increased levels of group-level learning. RPC plays an essential part in formative assessment strategy as it offers the necessary scaffolding for the student to work interdependently on goal achievement and feedback giving [16].

Peer coaches do not need to be experts. They need to ask the right questions to create more deep thinking about the performance quest. More often than not, coachees will be able to work through problems themselves and discover their solutions. The peer coach merely serves as a respected guide that gains the peer coachee's trust and respects over time due to the positive changes seen in learning and performance. This process is different from mentoring, which is often confused with coaching. Mentoring is very status-driven because the mentor is seen as a wise and experienced individual. The mentor adopts the mentee and provides unilateral advice and support in a one-way direction from mentor to mentee. It is distinct from peer coaching, which is often reciprocal and driven from the bottom up by the coachees who set the goals and objectives for their development [17].

Peer coaching in teaching is considered an effective method for improving student learning by supporting teachers through a collaborative and reciprocal process of reflecting on and improving teaching practice. Peer coaching typically involves two teachers agreeing to identify areas of focused attention, observing each other's teaching practices, sharing ideas for effective teaching, and reflecting together on the process. A key conceptual premise is that teachers can learn from their peers' feedback in a no evaluative partnership [18].

Emotional Intelligence. An emotionally intelligent coach can see the relationship between the personality traits and type of communicative behaviour and can form a high potential team in terms of its ability to perform in the competition. An emotionally intelligent coach can see that individual differences of team members can result in problems in mutual activity. To create a proper psychological climate in the team, to develop an athlete's mastership, a coach must reflect on his/her strengths and weaknesses and have reasonable impulse control, especially under conditions of failure, rejection, and aggression. Personality traits of sportspeople and coaches in their complex relationships could reveal themselves in a pretty different way – assisting or hindering the performance under stress, assisting or making any conflict resolution difficult, etc. The whole atmosphere in a team depends on the coach responsible for establishing psychological contact with all team members to evaluate everyone. The coach plays a central role both in preparation for the event and during

the competition, and it is of great importance which ways or styles he/she used to employ. According to the situation, the coach should be able to switch from one style to another [19].

Team Working. Teamwork is commonly required in the industry. At university, students learn teamwork by working in groups, for example, during a software development assignment. Teamwork affects their productivity. Lecturers evaluate their overall group performance. Lecturers also need to assess the cooperation of each team member. Cooperation data comes from the students involved, e.g., via questionnaire. Here we draw attention to specific items for assessment. We then show how to merge or aggregate evaluations using the lecturer's overall quality scale and the students' peer assessment scale. To this end, we will explain and demonstrate the underlying Split-Join Invariance principle using two compatible scoring formulae [20].

One study raised awareness about the categories and items that need to be assessed for teamwork results. It showed how we could get student ratings for the cooperation, e.g., in a software team, based on peer ratings by other team members. It has also given a scoring rubric for the lecturer to mark the group. Finally, the work has shown how to consistently, robustly, and reasonably combine these into an aggregated evaluation for the student's reports, all based on the essential Split-Join-Invariance principle. We also provided some example scoring functions [20].

Empathy. The alliance's strength referred to the extent to which the relationship was built upon trust, empathy, positive regard, and genuineness. These conditions refer to the core conditions. It was commented that if certain conditions existed, the interpersonal relationship and process would bring about greater integration, less internal conflict, more utilizable energy for practical living, and changes in behavior. The quality of the relationship was an essential contributor to relationship success; indeed, when the partnerships were new, establishing trust at the onset was vital. When there was mutual trust, opportunities for social support were also created. The alliance could only be effective if the overall environment were one of safety and confidentiality [21].

Integrity. Self-integrity is one of the elements of a student's integrity during peer assessment. Self-integrity is defined as something that happens inside an individual or in his/her mind. In peer assessment, the self-integrity of a student influences the integrity of conducting the assessments that have several sub-elements. There are three sub-elements of self-integrity: self-motivation, courage or assertiveness, and self-discipline [22].

As basic dimensions, they point to appreciation and care, problem-solving, conflict and betrayal, helping and guiding, the frequency of socializing and recreation, and level of intimacy and self-detection. Some authors emphasize accessibility, shared activities, care, honesty, confidentiality, loyalty, understanding, compassion, sharing information, laughter, humor, and entertainment. It described the developmental course of a friendly relationship over three periods: early childhood (3 to 7 years), middle childhood (8 to 14 years), and adolescence (14 to 18 years). The qualities being sought in friends depend on the child's age. Younger children in early childhood emphasize the importance of play as an essential feature of friends. In contrast, preadolescents and early adolescents emphasize intimacy, loyalty, trust, and closeness as essential features of a relationship with a friend. In middle and late childhood, the best friend is called the person in whom the child is most confident, ready to co-operate, providing protection, support, and consolation [23].

Social Boldness. Consistent inter-individual differences in behaviour within populations referred to as personality variation is now widespread. Boldness is one such axis of personality variation, i.e., a personality trait, and describes consistent differences between individuals in their response to perceived risk. Boldness is generally considered part of a significant 'proactive-reactive' axis of personality variation. Boldness is a suite of behaviours including exploration, activity, and aggression that correlate positively with one another. Variation in boldness is believed to result from differences in a growth-mortality trade off, driven by bolder individuals having greater food intake when foraging but a higher risk from predation. These factors of foraging and risk are also significant determinants in whether individuals are leaders in groups. Leadership occurs when a single or small minority of individuals disproportionately influence group decisions, such as when and where to initiate behaviours. With more significant influence, leaders can determine group behavior by directing others to resources when the leaders are in greater need. In groups that are led from the front, leaders have greater access to encountered food [24].

As explored in the study, Peer Life coaching encompasses several perspectives among the experts who have given their efforts in studying the intervention. It is one intervention that focuses explicitly on the personal goals and aspirations of individuals. There are several definitions of life coaching that were provided and several related variables that give justification for it. Life coaching can be understood as a collaborative, solution-focused, results-oriented process in which the coach facilitates the enhancement of life experience and goal attainment in the personal and professional life of ordinary, non-clinical clients. Some key points revealed in the study that it works with individual relationships, group leadership, leadership discussion, advisory, tutorial, and human interpersonal activity discovered in the study. There was

insight among experts in the review that conducting peer life coaching to students or with peers may bring out better personal and reciprocal relationships. Those are the concepts that were tried to prove in this study

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher used the quantitative descriptive method since the study focused on the level of awareness on peer life coaching and the level of manifestation of reciprocal relationships among the junior high school students of Looc Integrated School. These are current conditions or situations. According to Calmorin [25], descriptive research seeks the actual facts concerning a current situation. In addition, its purpose is not only to find truth but to find a new one.

Paler-Calmorin explained that the descriptive method is valuable and indispensable to discovering truth and all its nuances. Likewise, quantitative research tests objective theories by examining the relationship among variables [26;27]. Furthermore, this also involves describing, researching, comparing, contrasting, and interpreting conditions that exist. The design is also appropriate to the study since it seeks awareness of peer life coaching and the level of manifestation of reciprocal relationships among the junior high school students of Looc Integrated School.

Research Instrument

The study utilized an adapted instrument/questionnaire to measure the level of awareness on peer life coaching and the level of manifestation of reciprocal relationships among the junior high school students of Looc Integrated School. The statistics limits with a 4-point Likert Scale with their corresponding verbal interpretation was used for the study.

The researcher utilized an adapted-modified research instrument/questionnaire. To validate its contents in terms of its reliability and applicability to the current study, it was tested among 15 randomly selected Grade 9 and 10 students of Looc Integrated School. Those students have experienced peer life coaching and are not included as sample respondents of the study. With the assistance of the statistician, the internal consistency of the instrument was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha.

Respondents/Participants of the Study

Table A shows the profile of the respondents of the study.

Table A: Profile of Respondents of the Study

INDICATOR	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Grade Level		
9	50	36
10	90	64
	140	100
Age		
13	3	2
14	33	24
15	84	60
16	19	13
17	1	1
	140	100
Sex		
Male	48	34
Female	92	66
	140	100

There are 140 Grade 9 and 10 students of Looc Integrated School who participated in the study. The majority of them (64%) are in Grade 10. Their ages ranged from 13 to 17. More than half (60%) are 15 years old. Further, 92 (66%) of them are female.

A random sampling procedure was used in selecting the respondents of this study. This technique was employed to ensure a fair or equal representation of students from each grade level included in the study. One hundred forty (140) students from Looc Integrated School were randomly selected to participate in the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

To achieve a smooth investigation on level awareness on peer life coaching and the level of manifestation of reciprocal relationships among the junior high school students of Looc Integrated School, the researcher sought first the permission of the Schools Division Superintendent of Calamba City to conduct the data gathering. After the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent, the letter of approval together with the survey questionnaire that will be distributed to the student-respondents was given to the principal of the Looc Integrated School. The questionnaires were collected on the agreed date and consolidated, followed by the tabulation of data. The consolidated data was submitted to a statistician for treatment.

Treatment of Quantitative or Qualitative Data

The following are the statistical treatments utilized by the researcher to answer the problems of the study: the frequency and percent distributions were used in presenting the profile of the student-respondents. This profile includes the grade level, age, and sex of the 140 student-respondents. The Mean was used to describe the level of manifestation of peer life coaching strategies, the level of personal relationship, and the level of reciprocal relationship among junior high school students. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was employed to establish the significant relationship between the level of manifestation of peer life coaching and personal relationship and the level of manifestation of peer life coaching and reciprocal relationship.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The junior high school students-respondents of Looc Integrated School were asked to assess the manifestation of peer life coaching in terms of six areas.

Specifically, these are in their individual relationship, group leadership, leadership discussion, advisory, tutorial, and human interpersonal relationship. This section provides the summary, analysis, and interpretation of their responses. The results specified the students' level of agreement in the different indicators of the six areas of peer life coaching.

Problem Number 1. What is the level of manifestation of Peer Life Coaching strategies among junior high school students of Looc Integrated School in terms of: Individual Relationship; Group Leadership; Leadership Discussion; Advisory; Tutorial; and Human Interpersonal Activity?

1.1 Individual Relationship

The study's first objective is to assess the level of manifestation of the student-respondents to peer life coaching in terms of individual relationships. Results of conducted inquiry on this matter are shown in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1 Level of Manifestation of Peer Life Coaching Strategies among JHS Students in terms of Individual Relationship

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 SD	2 D	3 A	4 SA		
I am sensitive with the needs of my schoolmates	2	8	88	42	3.21	A
I am compassionate	0	5	81	54	3.35	SA
I support my classmates struggles	3	6	62	69	3.41	SA
I am willing to learn more to help my friends better	0	4	38	98	3.67	SA
I am an active listener	1	4	49	86	3.57	SA
Composite Mean					3.44	SA
Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation		
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested		
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested		
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested		
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested		

As indicated in table 1.1., junior high school students perceived that their level of manifestation of Peer life coaching strategies on individual relationships obtained a composite mean of 3.44, which they strongly agree on statements. This implies that they fully manifested the individual relationship. Moreover, the highest mean obtained is on statement 4, indicating that they are willing to learn more to help friends better, with a mean of 3.67 interpreted as strongly agree or fully manifested. Furthermore, the lowest obtained mean is 3.21 on the statement that students are sensitive to their schoolmates' needs where they agree or manifested the concern.

Student-respondents show that peer life coaching with friends or classmates in school helps them learn more through each other's help, which posted the highest mean of 3.67 for they strongly agreed or fully manifested on the indicators set. There might be challenges or negative experiences that each one has but having inspirational moments with friends

around as you share viewpoints. The sharing that is conducted provides a positive avenue for individual relationships between and among students.

However, the views on being sensitive to the needs of their schoolmates posted the lowest mean of 3.21, which implies that students manifested this concern. Students are sensitive to some aspects that they know from their friends or classmates in school but do not consider this in posting individual relationships. A profound and essential discussion may require more intellectual limits yet is substantially more remunerating for a sensitive person.

According to Spence & Grant [28], coaches assisting the individual relationship of clients seek to accelerate goal attainment by helping individuals develop and implement solutions to the ongoing challenges faced. Most importantly, emphasis is placed on being compassionate and willing to learn the viewpoints and interests. This would post a more significant relationship between individuals.

1.2 Group Leadership

Table 1.2.Level of Manifestation of Peer Life Coaching Strategies among JHS Students in terms of Group Leadership

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 SD	2 D	3 A	4 SA		
I foster cooperative rather than competitive relationships among people I work with.	2	0	66	72	3.49	SA
I actively listen to diverse points of view.	0	7	61	72	3.46	SA
I treat others with dignity and respect.	1	4	39	96	3.64	SA
I support the decisions that other people make on their own.	1	3	54	82	3.55	SA
I give others a great deal of freedom and choice in deciding how to do their work.	0	6	54	80	3.53	SA
I provide opportunities for others to take on leadership responsibilities	0	5	53	82	3.55	SA
	Composite Mean				3.54	SA
Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation		
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested		
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested		
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested		
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested		

Another aspect of peer life coaching that was considered in the study is group leadership. Table 1.2 reveals the level of manifestation of the student-respondents to peer life coaching in terms of group leadership. The composite mean is 3.54, to which the student-respondents Strongly Agreed with the statements that they responded. The highest mean is 3.64 from the statement that student respondents treat others with dignity and respect, with which they strongly agreed or fully manifested the concern. On the other hand, the lowest mean obtained 3.46 that they actively listen to diverse views that they strongly agree or fully manifested.

For every peer life coaching session, students treat others with dignity and respect posted the highest mean of 3.64, indicating strongly agree or fully manifested. This coaching approach rebuilds students' respect for one another to showcase their shared ideas, feelings, and experiences to others in the process of helping one another enhance their soft skills and collectively resolve current relationship issues. On the aspect of providing opportunities for others to take on leadership responsibilities, doing peer life coaching provides an opportunity for students to learn from their experiences to foster their dignity rather than taking them away from their experiences to learn. It enables them to accept challenges and responsibilities to become leaders of other peer life sessions.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.46, which the students strongly agreed, is in terms of students being *active listeners to their peer's points of view*. This shows that the student-respondents fully manifest this perspective. Students during peer life coaching listen attentively to their coaches that they tune in for important aspects that they need to learn. The student-listeners show sympathy, acknowledgment, and validity. For this instance, group leadership in terms of active listening is moderately manifested.

Students in the peer life sessions through group leadership show these meaningful pursuits; life coaches, according to Spence & Grant [28], help others get the most out of themselves and their lives by drawing out and building upon individual strengths and virtues. Viewed in this light, life coaching can rightly claim to represent “positive psychology in action” as a group activity leading and guiding one another.

1.3. Leadership Discussion

Table 1.3.Level of Manifestation of Peer Life Coaching Strategies among JHS Students in terms of Leadership Discussion

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 SD	2 D	3 A	4 SA		
We look ahead and communicate about what I believe will affect us in the future.	1	4	73	62	3.40	SA
We describe to within the group what we should be capable of accomplishing.	1	7	69	63	3.39	SA
We talk as a group about a vision of how we could be even better in the future.	0	7	53	80	3.52	SA
We talk as a group about how their own interests can be met by working toward a common goal.	0	3	59	78	3.54	SA
We are upbeat and positive when talking about what we can accomplish.	0	5	67	68	3.45	SA
We speak with passion about the higher purpose and meaning of what we are doing.	2	6	75	68	3.34	SA
Composite Mean					3.44	SA

Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested

The third aspect of peer life coaching in the study is leadership discussion. Table 1.3 presents the level of manifestation of the student-respondents to peer life coaching strategy in terms of leadership discussion. The composite mean is 3.44, which they strongly agreed on the statements given. This means that the student-respondents fully manifested peer life coaching on leadership discussion. The highest mean obtained is 3.54. Student-respondents strongly agreed that they talk as a group about how their interests can be met by working toward a common goal at a fully manifested level. On the other hand, the lowest obtained mean is 3.34 that student-respondents strongly agreed that they speak with passion about the higher purpose and meaning of what they are doing that signifies their fully manifested level.

The highest weighted mean of 3.54 or strongly agree *on how their interests can be met by working toward a common goal*. This implies that they fully manifested the perspective. There must be reasonable goals to be set in conducting peer-life coaching that can affect each student's emotional wellness. Nevertheless, it can likewise assist coaches/ student coaches in beating the conflicts raised and will help them recover. Goal setting goes about as a guide for students to follow regarding defeating difficulties and accomplishing things throughout their everyday life.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.34, which is strongly agree, is *speaking with passion about the higher purpose and meaning of what they are doing*. This further highlights the awareness of student-respondents about peer life coaching. Coaches in the process of coaching have an enthusiasm to help other people understand their higher purpose. They exhibit regard for those they serve and comprehend their parts inside the guiding cycle to comprehend the meaning of what they are doing.

At Luthra & Dahiya [29] discussed, the excellent communication abilities of the coaches uphold in making a climate for excellent understandings of what is being conveyed and urge students to follow their leaders indiscriminately. In this way, turning into a specialist in initiative correspondence is essential for leaders who need to achieve greatness towards a common goal to be attained for a quality-of-life experience of one another. This would help them realize the true meaning of counseling.

1.4. Advisory

Table 1.4. Level of Manifestation of Peer Life Coaching Strategies among JHS Students in terms of Advisory

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 SD	2 D	3 A	4 SA		
I know the types of support and services I can get from Advising in school.	4	14	90	32	3.07	A
Advising is important for my classroom study.	1	7	61	71	3.44	SA
Advising helps me understand my study options and other school	0	8	41	91	3.60	SA

requirements.

Advising helps me adjust to my high school life.	0	7	46	87	3.57	SA
Advising helps me plan for my study.	3	11	51	75	3.42	SA
I had expected some sort of support like advising before I became a student in Junior High School.	7	13	65	55	3.19	A

Composite Mean 3.38 SA

Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested

The fourth aspect of peer life coaching in the study is advisory. Table 1.4 reveals the level of manifestation of the student-respondents to peer life coaching in terms of advisory. The composite mean is 3.38, which is strongly agree. This means that advising as an activity of peer life coaching is fully manifested by the students. Moreover, the highest mean obtained from the indicators set is that advising helps students understand study options and other school requirements with 3.60 or strongly agree, indicating a fully manifested level. Lastly, the lowest mean obtained is 3.07 that student-respondents know the types of support and services they can get from advising in school, indicating manifested level.

The highest weighted means of 3.60 and 3.57, both strongly agree or fully manifested, believing that *advising helps the students understand their study options and other school requirements*. Attending peer life coaching posits academic advising to students, which plays an indispensable potential in connecting students with becoming acquainted with potential outcomes to encourage and uphold their commitment, achievement, and accomplish school activities.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.07, which is Agree or moderately manifested, is in terms of the student-respondents *knowing the types of support and advice that they can get from advising*. This implies that identifying the kind of support is moderately manifested by the students. They may have identified the different aspects that coaches can share in the process of counseling but are bounded by some limitations since there is a wide variety of assistance that can be given, which depends on the situation or issues to be raised during coaching time.

They are committing oneself to advise activity to peer life coaching, as Al-Khafaji [30] shared, guides the students to achieve their career goals smoothly in stipulated duration. In educational processes, academic advising provides the faculty and the student with face-to-face interaction to get clear ideas about the curriculum and the study plan.

1.5. Tutorial

Table 1.5. Level of Manifestation of Peer Life Coaching Strategies among JHS Students in terms of Tutorial

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 SD	2 D	3 A	4 SA		
Tutoring hours is convenient for me.	4	18	87	31	3.04	A
Tutoring is effective in providing services in one or more of my classes.	1	12	78	49	3.25	SA
Tutors are patient with me.	6	20	76	38	3.04	A
The tutors are knowledgeable of their subject area.	3	13	71	53	3.24	A
I become more proficient in working in groups with a tutor.	5	20	77	38	3.06	A
The personnel are courteous and helpful in answering any questions I had regarding tutoring services.	2	14	84	40	3.16	A
I became competent in the subject area I received tutor.	7	29	76	28	2.89	A
I can you work more independently in my subject area now.	1	16	80	43	3.18	A
I am confident in and positive about the subject area I received tutoring.	3	19	76	42	3.12	A
Composite Mean					3.11	A

Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested

The fifth aspect of peer life coaching in the study is tutorial. Table 1.5 presents the level of manifestation of the student-respondents to peer life coaching in terms of the tutorial. The composite mean is 3.11, which is Agree. This means that students manifested the tutorial activity on peer-life coaching. The highest obtained mean is 3.25, which

indicates that tutoring effectively provides services in one or more of student's classes that are noted to be strongly agreed or fully manifested. Further, the lowest obtained mean is 2.89, which they agreed on becoming competent in the subject area which they received tutor that they manifested.

The highest weighted means of 3.25, which is strongly agreed or fully manifested, is believing that *tutoring is effective in providing services in one or more of the students' classes*. Conducting tutorials to assist academic challenges considers higher paces of students, which brings about better scholastic accomplishment. For the most part, students associated with peer life coaching show a more inspirational mentality toward learning and create fearlessness in all class activities. This makes them realize the effectiveness of the service provided and a moderate level of manifestation of peer-life coaching.

The lowest weighted mean of 2.89, which is also agreed or manifested, is in terms of the student-respondents believing that *they became competent in their subject areas where they have a tutor*. This implies a moderate level of manifestation as to their competence in the subject areas. Tutoring depends upon collaboration and cooperation among students. This implies that exercises should typically introduce chances for students to distinguish issues, pose inquiries, and clarify their thoughts. Through these, they may be able to understand entirely academic challenges for them to be competent afterward. Although the weighted means are comparatively smaller than the other aspects of peer life coaching analyzed in the study, the students' responses indicate their moderate level of manifestation of peer life coaching.

Research indicates that peer learning activities like tutorial typically yield the following results for both tutor and tutee according to Briggs [31] like team-building spirit and more supportive relationships, greater psychological well-being, social competence, communication skills and self-esteem and higher achievement and greater productivity in terms of enhanced learning outcomes.

1.6. Human Interpersonal Relationship

Table 1.6. Level of Manifestation of Peer Life Coaching Strategies among JHS Students in terms of Human Interpersonal Relationship

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 SD	2 D	3 A	4 SA		
I develop and maintain supportive relationships with others.	0	5	43	92	3.04	A
When it is appropriate, and speak directly and honestly with others about who I am, what I feel, and what I want.	3	6	72	59	3.25	SA
Other people tell me that I am a good listener.	5	16	77	42	3.04	A
I communicate my anger or upsets without blaming others.	2	25	72	41	3.24	A
I make and keep promises that require me to achieve my potential.	2	17	69	52	3.06	A
I know that some of my opinions and judgments come from my own cultural background, but I am open to understanding people with different backgrounds.	0	1	53	86	3.16	A
I have the ability to make friends and create valuable relationships in a new place.	1	7	70	62	2.89	A
I am open to being with people I don't especially like in order to learn from them.	2	10	87	41	3.18	A
Composite Mean					3.32	SA
Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation		
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested		
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested		
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested		
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested		

The last area of peer life coaching included in the study is in terms of human interpersonal relationships. The responses of the students are presented in Table 1.6. The composite mean is 3.32, which is strongly agree. This means that the students perceived that they fully manifest peer life coaching on human interpersonal relationships. The highest mean obtained is 3.25 or strongly agree on when appropriate, and speak directly and honestly with others about who the students are, what they feel, and what they want they fully manifested. Moreover, the lowest mean obtained is 2.89 or agree on making friends and creating valuable relationships in a new place considering that it is manifested.

The highest weighted means of 3.25, which is agreed or manifested, believes that *when it is appropriate, the students need to speak directly and honestly with others about who they are, what they feel, and what they want*. It is necessary to

ensure that students should be able to manifest honesty in sharing conflicts within themselves during peer-life coaching. During the human interpersonal activity, students advance transparency, engages them, and empowers them to present current realities. Moreover, being honest about what they feel shows a moderate level of manifestation.

The lowest weighted mean of 2.89, which is also agreed or manifested, is the student-respondents believing that *they can make friends and create valuable relationships in a new place*. Students who make companions and structure connections in school are bound to be scholastically fruitful in all their activities. Establishing friendship within and among students can help them realize their worth to empower them, will be more ready to confront the challenges in schools.

Studies have indicated that an absence of a human interpersonal relationship is hurtful to students' wellbeing and adjustments. Having a companion can function as a defensive factor for more associations with different students. Social connectedness established in peer-life coaching within and among students is reliably perceived as gainful to sound turn of events, including physical and psychological wellness, and has suggestions for student's adulthood [32].

Problem Number 2. How do student respondents describe their personal relationship as to: Positive Attitude; Diversity; and Building Relationship?

2.1. Positive Attitude

Table 2.1 Level of Manifestation of Personal Relationship among JHS Students in terms of Positive Attitude

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 SD	2 D	3 A	4 SA		
I choose my own words carefully and states own points clearly in order to avoid in order to avoid confusion about goals and expectations	1	3	79	56	3.37	SA
I try as much as possible to display a positive attitude even when one is feeling unhappy or stressed about a situation.	1	1	59	79	3.54	SA
I speak positively to colleagues and provides quality feedback about the people one works with.	1	3	90	46	3.29	SA
I write notes of appreciation to teachers and students who are doing exemplary work, makes positive contributions and goes beyond the call of duty.	15	20	69	36	2.89	A
I develop mutual respect; finds ways to show that one truly values other students' contribution to classroom task.	4	3	56	77	3.47	SA
I do my own job well and makes a point of finishing own task on time in order to gain respect from co teachers and students.	9	9	82	40	3.09	A
I practice common courtesy by making eye contact and referring to colleagues by their names in order to create a smooth working environment	10	15	71	44	3.06	A
Composite Mean					3.25	SA
Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation		
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested		
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested		
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested		
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested		

This part presents the responses of the students on how they describe their personal relationship in terms of having positive attitude, diversity, and building relationship. This section provides the summary, analysis, and interpretation of their responses in all these areas. The results specified the level of agreement of the students in the different indicators of the three areas of their personal relationship.

The first aspect of personal relationships among the junior high school students analyzed is their positive attitude. There are seven indicators used to assess this. As shown in Table 2.1, the composite mean of the students' responses is 3.25, which is interpreted as strongly agree. Hence, the students have fully manifested a good attitude and have a good personal relationship in this area. The highest mean obtained is 3.54. They strongly agreed or fully manifested to try as much as possible to display a positive attitude even when one is feeling unhappy or stressed about a situation. Moreover, the lowest mean obtained resulted in 2.89 whereas they agreed or manifested how they could write notes of appreciation to teachers and students who are doing exemplary work, make positive contributions, and go beyond the call of duty.

The students agree in almost all of the indicators, which indicates positive attitude is high. The highest weighted mean of 3.54, which is interpreted as strongly agree or fully manifested, is in terms of the students *trying as much as possible to display a positive attitude even when they are feeling unhappy or stressed about a situation*. This implies that the students have a strong positive attitude towards personal relationships. Developing a positive attitude despite the challenges that you experience tends students to figure out how to value all they have in their lives. Their family, companions, vocation, home, food, and so forth is sufficient to make an uplifting mentality. Regardless of how terrible things get throughout everyday life, we should appreciate all that we have. These might have been some of the reasons why students under study share a positive attitude toward personal relationships.

The lowest weighted mean of 2.89 (*Agree*), which makes students in manifested level, on the other hand, is in terms of *writing notes of appreciation to teachers and students who are doing exemplary work, making positive contributions, and goes beyond the call of duty*. You show your regard for individuals when you express appreciation for what they do more, if it is on their exemplary performances. They will be thankful and show you their thankfulness consequently. This positive attitude encourages students to perform even better, and personal relationships between teachers and students can be more established.

It is noted that people with a positive attitude are optimists and believe they are accountable for good things and that good thing will generally come their way. If something bad comes instead, optimists tend to write it off as an isolated incident, an anomaly, or something out of their control. They continue to believe things will be better in the future [33].

2.2. Diversity

The second aspect of personal relationships that were considered in this study is diversity. There are seven indicators used to assess this. Table 2.2 presents the weighted means and interpretations of the students' responses in each of the indicators. As shown in the table, the composite mean of the students' responses is 3.27, which is interpreted as strongly agree or with fully manifested level. This value indicates that the students are diverse in their personal relationships. The highest obtained mean is 3.40. Student respondents strongly agreed or fully manifested how to accept diverse people and take the time to consider their opinions and factor their insights into one's decision-making. On the other hand, the lowest mean participates in diverse activities that do not involve work with other teachers and students to establish more connection at work with a mean of 3.04 noting agree or manifested level.

Table 2.2 Level of Manifestation of Personal Relationship among JHS Students in terms of Diversity

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 SD	2 D	3 A	4 SA		
I demonstrate to colleagues that I am listening carefully by paraphrasing what they have said and asking follow-up questions depending on their diverse personality.	5	8	85	42	3.17	A
I accept diverse people and takes the time to consider their opinions and factor their insights into one's own decision-making.	1	2	77	60	3.40	SA
I cope with conflicts by listening actively and making sure to address the diverse situation only after both parties have had a chance to calm down.	1	5	84	50	3.31	SA
I participate in diverse activities that do not involve work with other teachers and students in order to establish more connection at work	7	11	92	30	3.04	A
I practice a deeper level of diverse awareness and pays attention to own actions in order to avoid damaging work relationships.	2	6	82	50	3.29	SA
I continue interacting with the person one has gotten to know in order to know each other better professionally and personally.	2	6	67	65	3.39	SA
Composite Mean					3.27	SA
Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation		
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested		
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested		
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested		
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested		

Looking at the different indicators, the highest weighted mean is 3.40, interpreted as strongly agree or with fully manifested level, is in terms of *accepting diverse people and taking the time to consider their opinions and factor their insights into one's decision-making*. Establishing good personal relationships considering diverse personalities allows students to be presented with groundbreaking thoughts, perspectives, customs, and points of view that constantly happen

when they interact. Students at this stage grow their views for understanding the world and the excellent learning environment in their school.

The lowest weighted mean is 3.04, interpreted as Agree or with manifested level, in terms of *participating in diverse activities that do not involve work with other teachers and students to establish more connections at work*. Notice that the students agree on all indicators. Experiencing new ideas, qualities, and practices in diverse activities set by teachers and students prompts thinking in more profound, more unpredictable, and more innovative ways instead of encouraging past thoughts and perspectives. Students who experience the most diverse classroom activities are more occupied with emotional reasoning cycles and grow more academic and scholarly abilities.

According to Hughey [34], coaches in peer-life coaching promote and maximize success for all students and help create a climate where diversity is celebrated. This success is built on providing counseling and an educational environment/climate that embraces all students' academic, personal/social, and career needs. Like many other educators, the roles of peer counselors are being restructured and expanded to meet the ever-changing needs of students, families, and schools considering a variety of diverse students, including multicultural students, who have many learning needs. There is a need for new strategies and resources to enhance and maximize all students' academic, personal/social, and career development.

2.3. Building Relationship

Table 2.3. Level of Manifestation of Personal Relationship among JHS Students in terms of Building Relationship

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 SD	2 D	3 A	4 SA		
I share my own knowledge, personality, and expertise at meetings in order to be more approachable and build relationships.	2	4	52	81	3.50	SA
I create time to chat with other students in order to know and learn about them and develop healthy and positive relationships.	4	8	52	76	3.43	SA
I help other teachers in their tasks or projects in order to improve own professional skills and create a more connected working relationship.	14	18	72	36	2.93	A
I show up on time every day and volunteers to lead others on a new project in order to demonstrate reliability and develop positive relationships.	10	18	80	32	2.96	A
I initiate a conversation by asking questions, sharing something about oneself and allowing the other person to share.	2	7	58	72	3.41	SA
I share information or content with others that is directly related to their work in order to help improve their professional skills.	2	6	59	72	3.42	SA
I introduce oneself to colleagues at social work events such as retreats, holiday parties, and conferences in order to know them better	7	18	72	42	3.05	A
Composite Mean					3.24	A
Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation		
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested		
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested		
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested		
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested		

The third aspect of personal relationships that was considered in this study is terms of building the relationship. To assess the students' personal relationship in this area, seven indicators were considered. Table 2.3 shows the weighted means and interpretations of the students' responses in each of the seven indicators of building the relationship. As shown in the table, the composite mean of the students' responses is 3.24, which is interpreted as Agree. This value indicates the manifested level of building relationships among the students. The highest mean obtained is 3.50, indicating a response of strongly agree or fully manifested in sharing student respondent's knowledge, personality, and expertise at meetings to be more approachable and build relationships. Moreover, the lowest obtained mean is 2.93. They agreed or manifested helping other teachers in their tasks or projects to improve their professional skills and create a more connected working relationship.

Among the ten indicators, the highest weighted mean is 3.50, interpreted as strongly agree or with fully manifested level, in terms of *sharing their knowledge, personality, and expertise at meetings to be more approachable and build relationships*. Building and cultivating connections among students by sharing the knowledge and experiences that they have makes a sensation of the network, which may affect every student's behaviour and learning in the class. Students

need to figure out how to perceive the qualities and aptitudes that every individual brings in the classroom and search for opportunities to expand on those abilities in the most area of need in building the relationship.

The lowest weighted mean is 2.93, interpreted as Agree or with manifested level, in terms of *helping peers in their tasks or projects to improve their professional skills and create a more connected working relationship*. Helping other peers with difficulties, particularly on their task, is noteworthy and gives students a brief look at another viewpoint. They figured out how to be more caring and understanding with others as well as with themselves. In any school-related activities, when something was troublesome, they discovered they could handle it through challenging work and diligence if they help one another. This is an attribute of a good working environment set to build good relationships within and among students.

To ensure that positive relationship in schools is to be attained, according to Ballantyne [35], there is a need for building a positive, inclusive, respectful school culture. There is a reduced need for severe interventions, as students are more engaged in school, are happier about the way things are done at school. There are processes in place to sort things out before they grow too large. This would help build a better relationship among students.

Problem Number 3. What is the level of the reciprocal relationship of the student respondents in terms of: Emotional Intelligence; Team Working; Empathy; Integrity; and Social Boldness?

This part presents the students' responses on how they describe their reciprocal relationship in terms of emotional intelligence, teamwork, empathy, integrity, and social boldness. This section provides the summary, analysis, and interpretation of their responses in all these areas. The results specified the students' level of agreement in the different indicators of the five areas of their reciprocal relationship.

3.1. Emotional Intelligence

Table 3.1. Level of Manifestation of Reciprocal Relationship among JHS Students in terms of Emotional Intelligence

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 VI	2 MI	3 MA	4 VA		
Am able to fit into any situation.	4	18	86	32	3.04	A
Often feel awkward around people.	4	27	54	55	3.14	A
Have the ability to make others feel interesting.	2	27	65	46	3.11	A
Get along well with few people.	1	18	65	56	3.26	SA
Know what makes others think.	6	21	76	37	3.03	A
I find it easy to handle myself in a new social situation.	48	65	18	9	1.91	D
Get along well with people I have just met.	12	31	64	33	2.84	A
Find it easy to relate to people.	25	59	45	11	2.30	D
Am good at sensing what others are feeling.	6	14	75	44	3.11	A
Find it easy to fit in.	12	40	47	41	2.16	D
Composite Mean					2.79	A

Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested

The first aspect of reciprocal relationships that this study focused on is terms of emotional intelligence. To assess the students' reciprocal relationship in this area, ten indicators were considered. Table 3.1 presents the weighted means and interpretations of the students' responses in each of the ten indicators of emotional intelligence. As shown in table, the composite mean of the students' responses is 2.79, which is interpreted as Agree. This value indicates manifested emotional intelligence among the students. The highest mean obtained is 3.26, which student-respondents agreed or manifested of getting along well with few people. The least observed mean is finding it easy to handle me in a new social situation where student-respondents disagreed or slightly manifested having a 1.91 mean.

Among the ten indicators, the highest weighted mean is 3.26, interpreted as strongly agree, is in terms of *getting along well with few people*. It shows that students are timid and felt awkward around new individuals, uncertain of what to tell, or stressed over others' opinions about themselves. This attribute of being awkward is fully manifested in showing reciprocal relationships with others.

The lowest weighted mean is 1.91, interpreted as disagree, *finding it easy to handle myself in a new social situation*. It is noticeable that the students find most of the indicators slightly manifested. It is observed that student-respondents slightly consider to handle themselves in socializing with others shows that they favored being in their own inventive spaces. Some students with social constraints prefer it that way even though they yearn for a more excellent resolution of understanding the reciprocal relationship experienced.

Mohzan, Hassan, & Abd Halil, [36] recognizes the influence of this non-cognitive ability in the success of a student's life. He posits that the "ability to manage one's emotions, to be able to validate one's feelings and to solve problems of a personal and interpersonal nature is essential for being academically successful. Additionally, academic performance appears to be facilitated by being able to set personal goals as well as to be sufficiently optimistic and self-motivated to accomplish them. This gives credit to ensuring positive emotional intelligence in fostering the reciprocal relationship among students.

3.2. Team Working

Table 3.2. Level of Manifestation of Reciprocal Relationship among JHS Students in terms of Team Working

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 VI	2 MI	3 MA	4 VA		
Am good at working with a group.	5	19	67	49	3.14	A
Always attend group meetings or team practices.	4	14	57	65	3.31	SA
Prefer to do everything with the group.	51	57	19	13	1.96	D
Enjoy being part of a group.	0	13	61	66	3.38	SA
Work best when I am with the group	51	53	28	8	1.95	D
Support my teammates or fellow group members.	3	14	47	76	3.40	SA
Share opinion with others	53	53	27	7	1.91	D
Feel I must respect the decisions made by my group.	2	3	41	94	3.62	SA
I think it's unimportant to socialize with others.	28	33	40	39	2.64	A
Work best when I am in a group.	5	20	72	43	3.09	A
Composite Mean					2.84	A

Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested

The second aspect of reciprocal relationship that this study focused on is terms of team working. To assess the students' reciprocal relationship in this area, ten indicators were considered. Table 3.2 shows the weighted means and interpretations of the students' responses in each of the ten indicators of the team working. As shown in the table, the composite mean of the students' responses is 2.84, which is interpreted as agree. This value indicates good team working among the students. The highest mean is 3.62, in which student-respondent strongly agreed or fully manifested the feelings that they must respect the decisions made by the group. Moreover, the lowest obtained mean is 1.91, indicating that the respondents disagreed on sharing opinions with others, which slightly manifested this concern.

Among the ten indicators, the highest weighted mean is 3.62, interpreted as strongly agree, is in terms of *feeling that they must respect the decisions made by their group*. It is more like students do not develop and advance by giving disagreement with others. They have developed a sense of respect by picking up new knowledge, assessments, and viewpoints of their colleagues in the group. With this, teamwork will be fully manifested in a reciprocal relationship.

The lowest weighted mean is 1.91, interpreted as disagree, to share *opinions with others*. Making time to share your opinions with other students encourages building up their self-confidence and begin to take in what others anticipate from them. Student-respondents viewed this indicator to be moderately inaccurate for they have not considered well their social association in sharing opinions with other students and have not established that well reciprocal relationship which they slightly manifested to establish teamwork.

According to Hwang [37], it is generally accepted that effective teamwork is characterized by good communication and collaboration among team members as they work toward achieving the common goal. The outcome or product of team performance is known as team effectiveness, which can be measured in different ways, including objective and self-reported team effectiveness and member satisfaction.

3.3. Empathy

Table 3.3. Level of Manifestation of Reciprocal Relationship among JHS Students in terms of Empathy

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 VI	2 MI	3 MA	4 VA		
1. I anticipate the needs of others.	1	9	82	48	3.26	SA
2. I am able to understand people who get emotional.	0	10	52	78	3.49	SA
3. I sense others' wishes.	4	20	79	37	3.06	A
4. I am interested in other people's problems.	14	38	59	29	2.74	A
5. Reassure others.	2	14	77	47	3.21	A
6. Seldom get emotional.	5	22	67	46	3.46	SA
7. Am concerned about others.	4	6	51	79	3.50	SA
8. Am affected by other people's happiness.	23	45	51	21	2.50	A
9. Have a good word for everyone.	4	11	80	45	3.19	A
10. I like being around happy people when I'm feeling sad.	32	34	43	31	2.52	A
Composite Mean					3.09	A

Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested

The third aspect of a reciprocal relationship considered in this study in terms of empathy has ten indicators that were looked into in assessing students' reciprocal relationship in this area. The weighted means and interpretations of the students' responses in each of the ten indicators of empathy can be found in Table 3.3. The composite mean of the students' responses is 3.09, which is interpreted as agree or manifested. This value indicates that the students have a good level of empathy. The highest mean obtained in the table is 3.50 on others, which established a strongly agreed or fully manifested indicator. On the other hand, the lowest mean is 2.74, which student-respondents agreed or manifested indicator on being interested in other people's problems.

Among the ten indicators, the highest weighted mean is 3.50, interpreted as strongly agree or fully manifested. This is in terms of *having concern about others*. Student-respondents showed concern and make their classmate realize that they care. During this process, they show empathy; they tune in with their complete consideration, are merciful, and express with utmost concern what others feel. Through this, they are very accurate in expressing empathy to foster reciprocal relationships.

The lowest weighted mean is 2.52, interpreted as agree or manifested, which is the *likelihood of being around happy people when feeling sad*. One of the best ways to find happiness is to find those who know how to nurture and create their happiness and share it freely. Spend time around these people, and you'll find yourself seeing the world differently. Since the students-respondents on this end show that they are moderately accurate with the statement, it only shows that during tough times that they are sad, they ensure that friends and family members are there, which makes them happy to deal with concerns. They show empathy to establish a reciprocal relationship.

Developing empathy, as described by Hammer [38] is possible only if students are willing to at least temporarily or occasionally let go of separate egocentric self-awareness and the incessant mind chatter and narcissistic emotional dramas that involves, so that they are not distracted from non-dualistically tuning into the experiential states and living energy presence of another person, with deeply invested heartfelt caring feeling as well as with our undivided fully invested conscious attention.

3.4. Integrity

Table 3.4. Level of Manifestation of Reciprocal Relationship among JHS Students in terms of Integrity

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VI
	1 VI	2 MI	3 MA	4 VA		
1. I avoid lying just to get myself out of trouble.	23	50	51	16	2.43	D
2. Am trusted to keep secrets.	5	7	65	63	3.33	SA
3. Am easy to understand.	39	58	35	8	2.09	D
4. Keep my promises.	3	19	62	56	3.22	A

5. I am transparent.	18	36	36	50	2.84	A
6. Believe that honesty is the basis for trust.	2	8	33	97	3.61	SA
7. Like to settle down troubles.	24	41	39	36	2.38	D
8. Can be trusted to keep my promises.	1	12	59	68	3.39	SA
9. I stand with my own principles.	22	78	31	9	2.19	D
10. Am true to my own values.	2	12	54	72	3.40	SA

Composite Mean 2.89 A

Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested

The fourth aspect of reciprocal relationship that this study focused on is terms of integrity. Ten indicators were considered in assessing students' reciprocal relationships in this area. The composite mean of the responses of the students is 2.89, which is interpreted as agree. This value indicates that the students have a good level of integrity. Moreover, the highest mean obtained is 3.61, strongly agreed by student-respondents indicating that they fully manifested believing that honesty is the basis for trust. On the other hand, the lowest mean is 2.09, which was disagreed by most student-respondents as they slightly manifested the easy-to-understand concept of integrity.

Among the ten indicators, the highest weighted mean is 3.61, interpreted as strongly agree. This is in terms of *believing that honesty is the basis for trust*. The student-respondents in the study are accurate on how they treat others both internally and externally. Being straightforward with themselves and with others is the first and most significant action towards enjoying, interpreting, and growing from their experiences in school. They are adequate to foster reciprocal relationships with others.

The lowest weighted mean is 2.09, interpreted as disagree, which is *easy to understand*. This implies that the student-respondents slightly manifested to set to be understood by their classmates. Through awareness and knowledge of your authentic self, it is through awareness and knowledge that can help you be understood by others, which is the foundation of ethical behavior. When others well understand a person during peer-life coaching, you can have integrity with other people and situations.

Students on this end, according to Connelly, Crook, Combs, Ketchen Jr., & Aguinis[39], intuitively believe that those with high integrity will not engage in dishonest behaviour. In contrast, those with low integrity can be either honest or dishonest. Therefore, any occasion wherein a student appears to act unethically suggests that the student has low integrity because a partner with high integrity presumably would not behave that way.

3.5. Social Boldness

Table 3.5. Level of Manifestation of Reciprocal Relationship among JHS Students in terms of Social Boldness

Indicators	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	1 VI	2 MI	3 MA	4 VA		
1. Am good at making impromptu speeches.	14	53	51	22	2.58	A
2. I am confident to give a speech in public.	54	44	23	19	2.05	D
3. Feel okay being the center of attention.	29	42	43	26	2.47	D
4. Keep in the background.	5	23	70	42	3.06	A
5. Feel comfortable around people.	10	35	58	37	2.87	A
6. Find it easy to approach others.	34	58	41	7	2.15	D
7. Have leadership abilities.	14	36	61	29	2.75	A
8. Detest being the center of attention.	7	47	58	28	2.76	A
9. Have a strong personality.	8	23	52	57	3.13	A
10. Have little to say.	15	23	56	46	2.95	A

Composite Mean 2.68 A

Legend:	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Symbol	Equivalent Interpretation
	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	SA	Fully Manifested
	2.50-3.24	Agree	A	Manifested
	1.75-2.49	Disagree	D	Slightly Manifested
	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	SD	Not Manifested

The fifth aspect of reciprocal relationship that this study looked into is in terms of social boldness. Ten indicators were considered in assessing students' reciprocal relationships in this area. The weighted means and interpretations of the students' responses in each of the ten indicators of integrity can be found in Table 3.5. The table reveals that the composite mean of the students' responses is 2.68, which is interpreted as agree. This value indicates that the students have manifested social boldness. The highest mean obtained from the indicators is 3.13, stating that student-respondents manifested strong personalities. Moreover, the lowest obtained mean is 2.05 which the indicator being confident to give a speech in public was disagreed, showing a slightly manifested indicator.

Among the ten indicators, the highest weighted mean is 3.13, interpreted as agree. This is in terms of *having a strong personality*. *Character strengths* are the positive qualities that the student-respondents of the study have, which might be reflected in their thoughts, feelings, and actions that promote the well-being of themselves and others. Each student has a unique profile of strengths, with some strengths being more developed and others less so, regardless of how they compare to other students. Moreover, it is good that students on this end are moderately accurate with the strong personality they have in posting reciprocal relationships.

The lowest weighted mean is 2.05, interpreted as disagree, *confident to give a speech in public*. Students slightly manifested this indicator based on their experience on numerous stages in life for vocation advancement where they need leadership abilities. Students' leadership skills are needed to accept challenges, solve problems, analyze career direction, and even give a speech in public or a group of people. This should be developed to them to establish well social boldness in showcasing a reciprocal relationship.

Social Boldness as described by Bevan, Gosetto, Jenkins, Barnes, &Ioannou[40] is generally considered to be part of a major 'proactive-reactive' axis of personality variation, where Boldness is one of a suite of behaviours including exploration, activity, and aggression that correlate positively with one another. Variation in Boldness is believed to result from differences in a growth-mortality trade-off, driven by bolder individuals having greater food intake when foraging but a higher risk from predation. These factors of foraging and risk are also significant determinants in whether individuals are leaders in groups.

Problem Number 4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of peer life coaching and personal relationship?

Table 4.Test of Significant Relationship between Peer Life Coaching and Level of Manifestation of Personal Relationship

Paired Variable	Correlation Coefficient (ρ)	Interpretation	Decision	Remarks
Relationship individually and..				
Positive Attitude	0.27*	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Diversity	0.26*	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Building Relationship	0.14	Very small positive correlation	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Group leadership and..				
Positive Attitude	0.25*	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Diversity	0.24*	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Building Relationship	0.31*	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Leadership discussionand..				
Positive Attitude	0.49*	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Diversity	0.51*	High positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Building Relationship	0.44*	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Advisory and..				
Positive Attitude	0.37*	Small positive		

		correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Diversity	0.21*	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Building Relationship	0.37*	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Tutorial and..				
Positive Attitude	0.55*	High positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Diversity	0.40*	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Building Relationship	0.40*	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Human interpersonal relationship and..				
Positive Attitude	0.55*	High positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Diversity	0.52*	High positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Building Relationship	0.45*	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant

*Significant at 5%, **Significant at 1%

The relationship between the student respondents' level of awareness of peer life coaching and their personal relationship is revealed in Table 4. The different aspects of peer life coaching and personal relationships were paired to analyze their relationship better.

Notice that the correlation coefficients are all positive. This indicates a positive relationship between peer life coaching and students' personal relationship in general. Furthermore, almost all of them are significant except for *relationship individuals on building* the relationship. Hence, the result establishes that better peer life coaching among students is positively and significantly related to their personal relationships. The other correlation coefficients indicate a very small positive correlation between the different aspects of peer life coaching and personal relationship.

The highest correlation coefficient of 0.55 to a positive attitude is tutorial and human interpersonal relationship, while the lowest correlation coefficient of 0.14 is between *relationships individually and building relationships*. There is a high positive and significant correlation with leadership discussion and diversity, while there is a minimal and insignificant relation between relationships individually and building relationships.

The power of peer influence as support to the result of the study, which is deliberated by Parker, Hall & Kram [41], has long been noted in psychological literature. The value of consulting with knowledgeable peers has been advocated both in coaching and in experiential learning. The sense of connection with others may be found in a range of personal relationships, including those with peers that provide formal and informal support. An increasing focus on the role peers can play in developmental relationships has highlighted a vital horizontal communication link. From a learning perspective, access to peers is critical to developing a community of practice.

Problem Number 5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of peer life coaching and reciprocal relationship?

Table 5. Test of Significant Relationship between Peer Life Coaching and Level of Manifestation of Reciprocal Relationship

Paired Variable	Correlation Coefficient (ρ)	Interpretation	Decision	Remarks
Relationship individually and				
Emotional intelligence	.255**	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Team Working	.330**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Empathy	.305**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant

Integrity	.176*	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Social Boldness	.285**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Group leadership and				
Emotional intelligence	.231**	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Team Working	.189*	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Empathy	.255**	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Integrity	.252**	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Social Boldness	.169*	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Leadership discussion and				
Emotional intelligence	.320**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Team Working	.325**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Empathy	.336**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Integrity	.139	Very small positive correlation	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Social Boldness	.196*	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Advisory and				
Emotional intelligence	.217**	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Team Working	.240**	Very Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Empathy	.350**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Integrity	.218**	Very small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Social Boldness	.287**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Tutorial and				
Emotional intelligence	.278**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Team Working	.388**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Empathy	.396**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Integrity	.276**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Social Boldness	.340**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Human interpersonal relationship and				
Emotional intelligence	.367**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Team Working	.386**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Empathy	.436**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Integrity	.192*	Very Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Social Boldness	.317**	Small positive correlation	Reject Ho	Significant

*Significant at 5%, **Significant at 1%

The relationship between the student-respondents' level of awareness of peer life coaching and their reciprocal relationship is presented in Table 5. The different aspects of peer life coaching (relationship individually, group leadership, leadership discussion, advisory, tutorial, and human interpersonal relationship) and reciprocal relationship (emotional intelligence, team working, empathy, integrity, and social boldness) were paired and their relationships were analyzed.

Peer life coaching in terms of *relationship individually* was significantly, but with a very small positive correlation, with *emotional intelligence* and *integrity* with a correlation coefficient of 0.255 and 0.176, respectively. On the other hand, *group leadership* has a significant and very small positive correlation with all the reciprocal relationship variables.

In terms of leadership discussion, it shows a very small positive relationship with social boldness with 0.196 but has no significant relationship depicted to integrity. Furthermore, very small positive relationships are depicted between advisory and reciprocal relationships as to emotional intelligence, teamwork, and integrity. All the variables of reciprocal relationship have a small positive relationship to a tutorial. Lastly, very small positive relationship between human interpersonal relationships and integrity. Hence, the results indicate that, in general, peer life coaching has something to do with reciprocal relationships, specifically in terms of advisory and tutorial.

Building and maintaining reciprocal relationships within a peer life coaching program takes time, according to Jarvis, et.al. [42], but can be helped along by starting with explicit norms for behavior and clear boundaries and expectations. These might include consideration of such factors as time, confidentiality, decision-making processes, participation requirements, and granting permission to inquire deeply, take risks, and experiment with an eye toward continuous improvement and learning for all participants.

Moreover, Peer Life Coaching is a robust learning methodology only when coaches successfully create trusting relationships with peers. This relationship forms a safety net essential to encourage the coach's learning partner to take risks necessary to improve instruction. It helps teachers face their fear factor.

Problem Number 6. Based on the findings of the study, what guidance program can be proposed towards the improvement of peer life coaching among junior high school students of Looc Integrated School?

Based on the findings of the study, the following guidance program is proposed towards the improvement of peer life coaching, and personal and reciprocal relationships of junior high school students of Looc Integrated School.

KEY RESULT AREA/ AREA OF CONCERN (based on results)	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	TIME FRAME	PERSONS INVOLVED	BUDGET	SUCCESS INDICATORS
Lack of confidence and well defined roles of Peer Coaches	To orient about the different roles and duties of Peer Coach/Peer Supporter	Project "PPSM" (Peer Progress Starts with Me)	August-March	Guidance Counselor Principal Advisers / Subject Teachers Students Officers (SSG) Volunteer students	5,000.00 for supplies and equipment funded by MOOE and donations from stakeholders	Assistance in daily management, it will be easier for students to managed difficult conditions in their daily lives. Social and emotional support, through empathetic listening and encourage-ment, peer coaches can help individuals cope with social
Afraid of others criticism	To develop self-esteem, confidence and positive feelings towards one-self					
Lack of skills in coaching	To promote peer coaching and among students of Looc Integrated School					

						or emotional barriers and stay motivated to reach their goals. On-going support, extended overtime, peer coaches successfully keep individuals engaged by providing proactive, flexible, continual follow-up.
Shortage of time to engage in peer coaching	To engage peer coaches to different peer coaching /peer guidance activities To develop camaraderie among students	“T.E.A. Time” (Time Extended to Assist Others)	August-March	Guidance Counselor Advisers / Subject Teachers Volunteer students	1,500.00 for supplies and equipment funded by MOOE and donations from stakeholders	On-going support, extended overtime, peer coaches successfully keep individuals engaged by providing proactive, flexible, continual follow-up
Difficulty in relating with other students	To promote collaboration among peer coaches and students To develop the importance of communicating with others	“Project C.O.D.E.” (Collaboration with Others despite Diversity to Empower Connection)	August-Marc	Guidance Counselor Principal Advisers / Subject Teachers Students Officers (SSG) Volunteer students	1,500.00 for supplies and equipment funded by MOOE and donations from stakeholders	Link people, peer coaches will serve as motivational link to promote positivity in sharing knowledge and experiences.

CONCLUSIONS/REFLECTIONS AND DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE USE

The student-respondents moderately manifested peer life coaching in terms of individual relationship, group leadership, leadership discussion, advisory, tutorial, and human interpersonal relationship, it shows that peer life coaching has influenced the students that have been surrounded by the peer life coaches.

The student-respondents have good personal relationship to which they possess positive attitude, with diverse understanding and built good relationship. This implies that through moderate manifestation of Peer life coaching, they were able to show good personal relationship between and among students. The student-respondents have good reciprocal relationship in terms of emotional intelligence, team working, empathy, integrity and social boldness. It means that students were able to establish reciprocal relationship with colleagues through their participation from peer-life coaching.

Peer life coaching and personal relationship are positively correlated. Whenever there is a moderate extent of manifestation of peer-life coaching, it enables them to establish good personal relationship with classmates. Peer life

coaching and reciprocal relationship are positively correlated. This concludes that the moderate level of manifesting peer-life coaching will yield to better reciprocal relationship between and among students. The developed guidance program may be implemented to ensure a well manifested peer life coaching in schools which may address better personal and reciprocal relationships among students.

The students' level of manifestation about peer life coaching can be improved by conducting trainings among potential peer life coaches. The students' level of personal relationship can still be improved through proper guidance activities that can be incorporated in a guidance program. Students need empowerment in to increase their level of reciprocal relationship. This can be done by formal and information training sessions. The guidance program should focus on improving the students' peer life coaching awareness. As this improves, personal relationship is expected to improve as well. The guidance program should focus on improving the students' peer life coaching awareness. As this improves, one can expect improvement in the reciprocal relationship of the students. The conduct of the guidance program which focuses on increasing the level of awareness of students in peer life coaching is essential in ensuring that their personal and reciprocal relationships become better.

REFERENCES

1. Kourkoutas, E. L. I. A. S., Vitalaki, E. L. E. N. A., & Fowler, A. (2015). Resilience based inclusive models for students with social-emotional and behavioral difficulties or disabilities. *Innovative practices for children and adolescents with psychosocial difficulties and disabilities*, 8-45.
2. DepEd Order (2018). Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of the Comprehensive Sexuality Education
3. Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological review*, 84(2), 191.
4. Lave, J. (1988). *Cognition in practice: Mind, mathematics and culture in everyday life*. Cambridge University Press.
5. Short, E., Kinman, G., & Baker, S. (2020). Evaluating the Impact of a Peer Coaching Intervention on Well-Being Among Psychology Undergraduate Students. *Coaching Researched: A Coaching Psychology Reader*, 285-296.
6. Eriksen, M., Collins, S., Finocchio, B., & Oakley, J. (2020). Developing students' coaching ability through peer coaching. *Journal of Management Education*, 44(1), 9-38.
7. Merian, D. Z., & Snyder, E. M. (2015). Peer Coaching in American Intercollegiate Athletics: An investigation of team dynamics, confidence and student-athlete learning. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*, 13(2), 81-100.
8. Alonso, F., Manrique, D., Martínez, L., & Viñes, J. M. (2015). Study of the influence of social relationships among students on knowledge building using a moderately constructivist learning model. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 51(4), 417-439.
9. Ash-Shiddiqy, A. A. R., Ash-Shiddiqy, A. R., Herdi, H., Hanim, W., & Robby, D. K. (2019, December). Model Guidance and Counseling by Using Role Playing Technique to Improve Students' Leadership Character. In *5th International Conference on Education and Technology (ICET 2019)* (pp. 274-276). Atlantis Press.
10. Suzen, E. (2021). Developing the guidance skills of SI leaders. *Supplemental Instruction Volume 2: Student Learning Processes*
11. Ellis, J. R., & Gershenson, S. (2020). Gender, peer advising, and college success. *Labour Economics*, 62, 101775.
12. Astuti, K. D., Sugiharto, D. Y. P., & Wibowo, M. E. (2018). Group Guidance with Role Play Techniques to Improve the Students' Interpersonal Communication. *Jurnal Bimbingan Konseling*, 7(2), 190-195.
13. Green, S., Grant, A. M., & Rynsaardt, J. (2020). Evidence-based life coaching for senior high school students: Building hardiness and hope. *Coaching Researched: A Coaching Psychology Reader*, 257-268.
14. Lujan, H. L., & DiCarlo, S. E. (2017). A personal connection: Promoting positive attitudes towards teaching and learning. *Anatomical sciences education*, 10(5), 503-507.
15. Possi, M. K., & Milinga, J. R. (2018). Learner diversity in inclusive classrooms: The interplay of language of instruction, gender and disability. *MOJES: Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 5(3), 28-45.
16. Porras, N. I., Díaz, L. S., & Nieves, M. M. (2018). Reverse mentoring and peer coaching as professional development strategies. *Colombian Applied Linguistics Journal*, 20(2), 169-183.
17. Ladyshevsky, R. K. (2017). Peer coaching as a strategy to increase learning and development in organisational life-a perspective. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*, 15(1), 4-10.
18. Sider, S. (2019). Peer coaching in a school in Cairo, Egypt: Implementation, barriers, and pathways to effective adoption. *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*.
19. Kim, A., Khon, N., & Aidosova, Z. (2016). Emotional intelligence of a coach as a factor of coach-student interaction. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 236, 265-270.
20. Kennedy, I. G., & Vossen, P. H. (2017). Teamwork assessment and peerwise scoring: Combining process and product assessment. *Bildungsräume 2017*.
21. Matthewman, L. J., Nowlan, J., & Hyvönen, K. (2018). Reciprocal peer coaching: A constructivist methodology for enhancing formative assessment strategy in tertiary education. *International Coaching Psychology Review*, 13(1), 35-47.

22. Abidin, N. A. Z., Masek, A., Faiz, N. S. M., & Sahdan, S. (2018). Exploring the Elements of Integrity in Peer Assessment. In *MATEC Web of Conferences* (Vol. 150, p. 05002). EDP Sciences.
23. Krampac-Grljusic, A., & Kolak, A. (2018). Peer relations in inclusive classes. *Research in Pedagogy*, 8(1), 17-35.
24. Bevan, P. A., Gosetto, I., Jenkins, E. R., Barnes, I., & Ioannou, C. C. (2018). Regulation between personality traits: individual social tendencies modulate whether boldness and leadership are correlated. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 285(1880), 20180829.
25. Calmorin, Dr. Laurentina Paler. 2010 Research and Statistics with Computer, National Bookstore. *Center for Public Education Journal*. (2007), p. 265.
26. Polit, D., & Hungler, B. (1994). Essentials of nursing research: Methods, appraisal, and utilization. *Journal of Nursing Staff Development*, 10(3), 175-178.
27. Moxham, L. (2012). Nurse education, research and evidence-based practice.
28. Spence, G. B., & Grant, A. M. (2007). Professional and peer life coaching and the enhancement of goal striving and well-being: An exploratory study. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*, 2(3), 185-194
29. Luthra, A., & Dahiya, R. (2015). Effective leadership is all about communicating effectively: connecting leadership and communication. *International Journal of Management & Business Studies*, 5(3), 43-48.
30. Al-Khafaji, S. (2017). Academic Advising process Roles in supporting student's success. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 5(11), 7485-7494.
31. Briggs, S. (2013). How peer teaching improves student learning and 10 ways to encourage it. Retrieved July, 14, 2019.
32. Buote, V. M., Pancer, S. M., Pratt, M. W., Adams, G., Birnie-Lefcovitch, S., Polivy, J., & Wintre, M. G. (2007). The importance of friends: Friendship and adjustment among 1st-year university students. *Journal of adolescent research*, 22(6), 665-689.
33. Kabir, S. M. S. (2013). Positive attitude can change life. *Journal of Chittagong University Teachers Association. Department of Psychology University of Chittagong, Chittagong*.
34. Hughey, J. (2011). Meeting the Needs of Diverse Students: Enhancing School Counselors' Experiences. *Educational Considerations*, 38(2), 20-27.
35. Ballantyne, R. (2011). Building a Culture of Positive Relationships: The Successful Implementation of Restorative Practices in Schools.
36. Mohzan, M. A. M., Hassan, N., & Abd Halil, N. (2013). The influence of emotional intelligence on academic achievement. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 90, 303-312.
37. Hwang, M. I. (2018). Relationship between teamwork and team performance: Experiences from an ERPsim competition. *Journal of Information Systems Education*, 29(3), 157-168.
38. Hammer, Barry. (2015). Developing Empathy. *Journal of Psychology & Clinical Psychiatry*. 10.15406/jpcpy.2016.05.00240.
39. Connelly, B. L., Crook, T. R., Combs, J. G., Ketchen Jr, D. J., & Aguinis, H. (2018). Competence-and integrity-based trust in interorganizational relationships: Which matters more?. *Journal of Management*, 44(3), 919-945.
40. Bevan, P. A., Gosetto, I., Jenkins, E. R., Barnes, I., & Ioannou, C. C. (2018). Regulation between personality traits: individual social tendencies modulate whether boldness and leadership are correlated. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B*, 285(1880), 20180829.
41. Parker, P., Hall, D. T., & Kram, K. E. (2008). Peer coaching: A relational process for accelerating career learning. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 7(4), 487-503.
42. Jarvis, R., Dempsey, K., Gutierrez, G., Lewis, D., Rouleau, K., & Stone, B. (2017). Peer Coaching That Works: The Power of Reflection and Feedback in Teacher Triad Teams. *McREL International*.